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Abstract: This article discusses the impact of social media on the younger generation and the positive and negative effects of social media on the younger generation.

Key words: public information, mass media, internet, internet network, information, social network, computer technologies.

Today, it is very difficult to imagine our life without social networks and the Internet. The main reason for this is that many people's work and educational processes are connected with social networks. This does not mean that everyone works on social networks. Because the majority of the population conducts their activities on social networks, and the rest use it in a relatively simple way. In simpler terms, it is intended to be aware of the changes taking place in the world, world news and daily news, and to communicate them to each other through social networks and telegram channels. In this place, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Let's pay attention to Mirziyoyev's speech about "Media".

"In recent years, about 290 private and departmental Internet publications with a large audience have been established in our country. Among other materials, they distribute the most important official information, normative legal documents in Uzbek, Russian and English languages.

Most importantly, it should be noted that the mass media comprehensively analyze the large-scale changes and renewal processes taking place in our country and draw the attention of state agencies and the public to local social problems, errors and shortcomings.

Of course, today we are searching in all areas, including the development of mass media. Therefore, along with achievements, it is natural that there will be shortcomings and defects along this path. Speaking about this, it is necessary to say that in our national media field, the sharp demands and criteria of the time, revealing the most important trends, critical analysis, boldly raising the topics and problems that people are waiting for are still not in the leading position. Unfortunately, most news media are still dominated by material with a light social weight, reportage and arrogance.

News about changes, events, and news happening in our country and the world are being reflected on social networks. It is very convenient to use internet system, mobile phones and computer technology to know about these news. In addition, social networks are a very convenient tool for exchanging information, reacting to events, expressing one's opinion or communicating. All this is a unique opportunity for users of social networks to express their thoughts, views and feelings. That is why social networks "fascinate" a person of any age to an unlimited extent.

Nowadays, we cannot imagine our life without the Internet. The number of young people entering the world information network is increasing day by day. Today, the most important issue is who uses the Internet and how. Nowadays, even young children can easily use the computer. At first glance, there is nothing wrong with this, but if it goes too far, if the control is relaxed, the consequences will be dire. As Chingiz Aitmatov wrote, it is not necessary to put a camel's skin on a person's bald head in order to turn a person into a manqurt. The wars that will take place now will not take place on the battlefield, but in the training ground of ideology. From this point of view, it is a great tragedy that young people spend so much time on the Internet. Because the Internet is used by people with bad intentions. The Internet has become the main weapon of hackers and third parties. They are "playing to their drums" our young people who do not know black and white, who cannot use the Internet properly. In this regard, we can take as an example the following thoughts of the honorable first President I.A. Karimov: "Of course, its incomparable value in establishing fast communication with any part of the world, obtaining information and information that is needed immediately, increasing knowledge and enlightenment through the Internet no one can deny that it has a role and importance. We fully support the aspirations of our people to use the Internet more widely. I want to say it again - to build some kind of wall in the world of information, to its own shell At the same time, if we take into account the events that are happening around us today, in far and near regions, there is a malicious plan aimed at misleading young people who have not yet formed their minds and life

views. It cannot be ignored that forces are also trying to use the Internet for their own interests, and what negative consequences such efforts can have."

Unfortunately, most young people use social networks all day, wasting their precious time. This, in turn, causes negative conditions for human health. Only 10 years ago, mobile phones were a symbol of social status. Today, young children cannot be surprised by this. Smartphones and phones have become an integral part of our lives. We literally cannot live without them. We have to admit that one day, if our smartphone or phone is left at home, we feel like a helpless person.

One of the main reasons for this is the increasing distribution of aggressive television, audio, video and multimedia products, information on the Internet and computer games in various ways. Today, in order to prevent such problems, as I.A. Karimov pointed out: "We must fight ideology against ideology, idea against idea, knowledge against ignorance. Because the spiritual and moral qualities in the hearts of our youth serve for noble goals. let him do it".

In conclusion, the Internet can be both good and bad. The task of young people is to use their opportunities for good and to take measures to guard against evil. Therefore, first of all, young people should learn and search for the value of stable peace and tranquility in our day, in order to protect this blessing like the apple of an eye.

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